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WORKSHEETS IN TEACHING ENGLISH**Toshtemirova Dinora Qurbonazar qizi**

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Annotation: in the article, the authors consider modern and innovative methods and means of teaching a foreign language, highlighting interactive worksheets. It is this means of organizing the learning activities of students that can be used at different stages of the lesson and respond to various educational tasks.

Key words: worksheet, information technology, internet, learning activities.

The work of a teacher in the modern world cannot be imagined without the use of information technology. In our world, these are not just technical means, but full-fledged forms and methods of teaching, the number of which is growing almost every day. It is becoming more and more difficult for a teacher to navigate this flow of information technology and choose exactly those tools that will be effective in the educational process.

We know that the task of a foreign language teacher is to create conditions for practical language acquisition for each student. This requires a competent approach when choosing methods and forms of education that would enable everyone to reveal their potential, show activity and creativity, and intensify cognitive activity in the study of foreign languages. Today, educational Internet resources perfectly cope with such tasks and, in addition, offer an individual approach to each student and differentiation of education, taking into account the abilities, interests and level of education of children.

I would like to draw your attention to the use of Internet information resources at the stage of implementing interactive methods, since this is the most accessible type of service that can be used during the lesson, even without full material and technical equipment for working online in the classroom.

There are a huge number of different sites for sharing experiences and presenting their so-called worksheets or worksheets, which are performed in text editors and represent several tasks united by the subject of the lesson. They can be different in form and content, they can be aimed at developing different language skills (phonetics, grammar, vocabulary, writing or speaking). Today we have an amazing opportunity to turn worksheets from simple printouts with tasks into entire interactive lessons. Probably, each teacher created his own worksheets in order to consolidate the material covered or to control knowledge, however, now we can use them as a method of presenting new knowledge, reinforcing the worksheet with a video or links to various services, such as GoogleMaps or Quzzlet.

This format of work is suitable for almost every teacher at any stage of the educational process. You have the opportunity to express your creativity and bring your ideas to life by creating your own interactive worksheet or using ready-made products.

An interactive worksheet (IRL) is an example of a means of organizing student learning activities. As a rule, it is developed by the teacher himself (as opposed to the situation when the teacher uses ready-made didactic materials) using cloud services and web tools, such as Googledocs, Zohocreator and others.

The prototype of the IRL are worksheets (worksheets), made in a conventional text or spreadsheet editor and widely used in teaching using a computer before the mass appearance of WEB 2.0 services. The function of joint editing and storage of documents, which cloud services have brought to the development of this type of didactic means, provides an important added value of materials created in the "clouds", interactivity. Other benefits of IRL include:

- the ability to copy a worksheet template;
- possibility of joint work;
- the ability to publish and embed ready-made documents in html - pages - student electronic portfolios.

Interactive worksheets, depending on their purpose, can be performed by students in pairs, individually in class or at home. It is very convenient and efficient to create such worksheets for homework. Cloud technologies allow you to create entire classes, develop and automatically check assignments, set marks, pin announcements and conduct a conversation with one or more students online, leave comments on work.

There are a lot of ways to create an IRL, as each teacher creates something unique. In general, the following are the most common methods:

- use of web quest elements
- problematic tasks united by a common theme or idea with elements of a role-playing game and with a step-by-step description of the stages;
- the inclusion of elements of the test, combining open and closed questions;
- development of a system of tasks for functional reading literacy when working with continuous and non-continuous texts;
- designing tasks for searching, selecting, transforming, interpreting information from the Internet;
- the use of a system of exercises aimed at developing the skills of structuring and classifying information, the ability to select the main and secondary, to schematize, etc.

Depending on the set learning task and the teacher's ability to construct IRL, work with interactive sheets may include a full cycle of learning activities - from immersing the student in the topic and posing a problem to evaluating the results of student work. Thus, the IRL can be a tool that organizes independent work. This is the activity of constructing new knowledge and mastering new ways of universal learning activities (UUD). It is suitable for both organizing homework and distance learning.

To create interactive worksheets, the tools included in the GoogleApps package for education are well suited: Google Docs - GoogleDocs, Google spreadsheets - Google spreadsheet, Google drawings - GoogleDrawings (Googledrawings worksheet creation technology).

As well as the Wizer service and the well-known LearningApps and ProProfs services.

Wizer (wizer.com) is an online service for creating interactive worksheets with the ability to insert any media material: video, image, text, audio file and use them in distance learning. It is possible to graphically design a worksheet, choose the design and templates for tasks yourself.

The service is convenient even for an inexperienced user, and besides, you can use it completely free of charge. There is a rich bank of ready-made didactic materials that you can also use absolutely free of charge.

LearningApps (learningapps.org) is a service for creating a variety of educational applications with tasks for filling in the blanks, connecting objects (words and images), mosaics, quizzes, the Hangman game, etc. You can also include links, videos, audio recordings, etc.

The disadvantage of LearningApps is that it is not possible to combine several created applications into one interactive worksheet. All created products are independent applications for which a huge selection of templates is offered. You can use the service completely free of charge, and it is also possible to use or edit already created applications for various subjects and topics. Learning Apps provides the ability to combine all applications by subject in your personal account, as well as create classes and give your students access to certain tasks.

So, in a world that is gradually becoming faster and more virtual, the task of the teacher is to keep up with the times and improve his arsenal of teaching methods and tools. Interactive worksheets are a great option for those who want to diversify the work of their students and complete all the tasks of the educational process.

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